

BLENDING LEARNING IN ESP INSTITUTION OF PHARMACY DIRECTIONS

Maksudova Khilola Ferdinantovna

*(PhD) Department of Practical English and Literature, National University
of Uzbekistan, Faculty of Foreign Philology.*

Tel: (90) 1850174, hilola-19833@mail.ru

Abstract

Nowadays using pedagogical technologies and information and communication technology in language teaching is tendency. Blended learning is new method in English for specific purposes courses in Uzbekistan. Teaching ESP students demands huge responsibility for ESP teachers as teaching content is not easy every time and BL can be useful in this case.

ESP students` and teachers` attitudes, advantages of conducting online courses in pharmacy directions were observed. This study was conducted with the 1st and 2nd year students of Tashkent pharmaceutical institute. Participants of this study were 100 students, ranging from 18-30, and 20 ESP teachers. In order to find the pharmacy students` attitudes towards using blended learning, all participants were interviewed. Data analysis revealed that ESP students of Uzbekistan have positive attitude to have blended courses in learning English.

Keywords: *English language teaching (ELT), English specific purposes (ESP), information communication technology (ICT), Blended learning (BL).*

Introduction

Development of science and technology requires specialists of different fields to be competent in English and ICT skills. To improve teaching and learning ESP in various fields ELT teachers and researcher are conducting many projects. ESP teachers implement different approaches as CLIL (content and language learning), task based approach, CLT (communicative language teaching) and BL is new

method in language teaching. It is obvious that students are eager to use technology and sometimes more competent than teachers.

Literature review

The first distance education began in the 1840's and in the 21st century, mixed education became a major part of education. Mixed Learning The term "blended learning" is a modern teaching method online lessons with face to face classes with interactive lessons, auditorial exercises interacting with one another online. Teaching ESP in blended learning settings was discussed and piloted by many ESP teachers and researchers as P.Sharma (2010), B.Tomlinson and C.Whittaker (2013), A. Daragmeh, S. Chirimbu and D. Tafazoli (2014), G. Kavaliauskiene (2011), I.Arguelles and L. Peco (2014). They discussed challenges and advantages of blended learning courses in ESP field. According to Sharma blended learning is a combination of technologies or a combination of methodologies as he considers blended learning is method. A. Daragmeh discusses challenges in implementing and using online courses in Palestinian tertiary institutions. As computer illiteracy of teachers and learners, wrong instructions of e-learning tasks demotivate learners to learn language. Another researchers S. Chirimbu and D. Tafazoli held research in Iran higher education's institutions and about 85% of students preferred learning language with technology and only 15% traditional classes. G. Kavaliauskiene shared with experience using blended learning to improve listening skill of ESP learners. According to I.Arguelles and L. Peco "blended learning courses is communication between instructor and learner is not only physical or necessarily immediate, as it allows a more flexible learning which adapts to the learner's disposition".

This is not just a matter of using computer technologies during the lesson, but also as a way to teach and learn a foreign language that is closely linked to classroom tutoring and online training in effective foreign language teaching. Its basic principles include:

- computer technology availability;
- the course has clear goals and objectives;
- online training sessions with audiences;
- compliance with the language needs of the learners;

Harker and Kautanthon (2007) have been shown to have had the effect of teaching English at an academically targeted English language, a network of specific learning environments. During the course of the mixing training course, online tutoring can be organized to develop reading and writing activities, to write reviews of relevant scientific articles, and to organize debate online forums.

Russian foreign language teachers say that the writing skills of future English teachers are reflected in students' comprehension of the essays included in the online platform by the students themselves.

There are three main purposes of using blended courses in ESP institutions:

Table -1

- 1) It can be used as extra activities to improve grammatical, phonetic, lexical competence. Most ESP institutions allocate less hours for language learning

because of subjects of specialty. In this case, student can do exercises and learn language.

- 2) It can also be used as independent work and it is assessed by teacher

Objectives of study

The objectives of this research is to evaluate pharmacy students` and English language teachers` attitudes and difficulties to conducts cooperative ESP classes.

Methodology

The data collected through the questionnaire and interview among 1st and 2nd year 100 students and 20 teachers Tashkent pharmaceutical institute. The questions of the questionnaire consist of 10 statements, to which students responded on a 3-pont, 1(agree), 2(not sure) and 3(disagree).

Results

10 statements of the blended learning questionnaire are shown in the table.

Statements		Agree	Not sure	Disagree
1.	Technology-based tools can be an effective method for learning English language.			
2.	Technology-based tools will enhance teacher –student interaction.			
3.	There are too many issues to use technology in ESP classes.			
4.	I prefer traditional classrooms rather than online courses.			
5.	Using technology is costly and ineffective in learning English for specific purposes.			

6.	Students can improve my listening and reading skills by blended learning courses.			
7.	Students can improve writing and grammar by blended learning courses.			
8.	Students can do extra activities and improve level of English.			
9.	I would like to participate in technology-based tools workshops for learning how to use these tools.			
10.	Teachers and students need administrative support to technology-based devices.			

Literature

1. Basturkmen H. Developing courses in english for specific purposes. University of Auckland, New Zealand. 2010. P-154.
2. Belcher D. English for specific purposes in theory and practice. / University of Michigan press. 2009. P-297.
3. Belyaeva A. English for Specific Purposes: Characteristic features and curriculum planning steps. // Sustainable multilingualism №7. 2015.-P.73-91.
4. Benavent G.T., Penamaria S.S. Use of authentic materials in the ESP classroom. // Encuentro 20, 2011. P. 89-94.
5. Berardo The Use of Authentic Materials in the teaching of Reading. The Reading Matrix 6.2: 2006. P.-60-69.
6. Canale, M. Theoretical bases of communicative approaches to second language teaching and testing / M.Canale & M.Swaine // Applied Linguistics. – 1980. – №1. – P.47–54.

7. Carter D. Some propositions about ESP// The ESP journal 2. 1983. –P.131-137.
8. Carter. R., Nunan D. The Cambridge guide to teaching English to speakers of other languages. / Cambridge university press. 2001. P. 274.
9. Chalekandy, Muhammed Ali. A comprehensive method for teaching English Specific Purpose. //Arab world English journal Vol. 4. 2013. P.- 310-322.
10. Gatehouse K. Key issues in English for Specific Purposes (ESP) curriculum development. // The internet TESL Journal 7(10). 2001. P.1-7.
11. Graves, K. A framework of course development processes.// In D.R. Hall, & A. Hewings (Eds.), Innovation in English language teaching. London: Routledge. 2001. P. 178-196.
12. Hymes, D. On Communicative Competence. In J.B.Pride and J.Holmes (eds.), Sociolinguistics. Harmondsworth: Penguin, 1972, – P.269-293.